

The Use of Translation Strategy and Translation Methods in Tourism Texts under the Guidance of Peter Newmark's Translation Theory: A Case Study of Everglades National Park, Florida

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ABSTRACT

With the rapid growth of the economy, people's pursuit of quality life is gradually increasing. Travelling abroad has become a hot topic nowadays. The rapid development of overseas travel has increased the demand for tourism translation and more stringent requirements for tourism translators. How to deal with the translation problems caused by the cultural differences between Chinese and English during the translation process is very important to improve the quality of tourism translation. The communicative translation strategy in Newmark's translation theory focuses on the effect that the translation brings to the target language readers, which is of certain guiding significance to the E-C translation of tourism texts. Therefore, this paper takes the Everglades National Park, Florida (Excerpt) as an example to analyze the specific translation strategies and methods in applying Newmark's translation theory in tourism texts to provide references for other translators.

1. Introduction

With the development of the world, various kinds of tourism appear in people's life and have unprecedentedly, extremely widely spread a variety of cultures and lifestyles. "Tourism has become a rising sunrise industry in modern society." To a foreign country to enjoy the beautiful scenery can make people know the colourful world and further know what they want. And this activity also has made tourism translation a reality and a thriving discipline. (Jin 2007: 32).

However, due to the different geographical environments, cultural differences and historical backgrounds in different countries, many translators often ignore the disadvantages brought by differences in language and cultural habits in the process of translation so that the original meaning of the original text will be lost in the process of transmission, which may cause confusion for tourists and cannot achieve the purpose of offering them accurate information and stimulating their interest.

Therefore, to make it more convenient for domestic citizens to travel abroad, translators should choose appropriate translation strategies and methods according to the cultural differences between China and foreign countries in English tourism translation so that tourists can form an objective and correct understanding of scenic spots. Yet, there is still a lack of research on these tourism texts. To address this issue, this paper highlights the use of semantic and communicative translation strategies in Peter Newmark's Theories, respectively focusing on whether the original text's meaning is exactly reproduced. The effect and influence the translation brings to the target language readers are of certain guiding significance to the English-Chinese translation of tourism texts.

In theory, based on Peter Newmark's translation theories, this paper chooses the semantic translation strategy. It puts forward appropriate translation methods for the English-Chinese translation of tourist text -the Everglades National Park, Florida (Excerpt), which is of certain guiding significance for the translation of tourist texts. Based on the practice of the Everglades National Park, Florida (Excerpt) English-Chinese translation and the analysis of Newmark's communicative translation strategy's application, this paper sums up some translation methods, such as voice change, objective and personal subject changing, adding conjunctions, etc. And these methods can be provided for future references in the translation study and practice of others, which has a certain practical significance.

2. Literature Review

Through the analysis of Newmark's communicative translation in recent years, it can be found that there are many references for the guidance of communicative translation on tourism translation texts. He (2005) proposes that the public notices and signs should belong to the vocative functional text and focus on the reader-centred communicative translation, which can give foreigners a better environment for travel, study and work in China. For such a style, the communicative translation theory should be chosen, the target readers put in the first place and always in mind, and their culture and receptivity taken into account. Jin (2006) believes that tour guide words must have a specific expected function, a kind of text that integrates informative, expressive and vocative functions. Therefore, tourism translation should aim to attract overseas tourists effectively, and the translator should grasp the group characteristics of overseas tourists and audiences when carrying out tourism propaganda or translating tourism materials. Ma (2010) points out that the tourism text is a kind of article mainly based on a vocative function, the core of which is to convey information to readers accurately. Liu (2013) proposes tourism text as a kind of publicity material to stimulate tourists' interest in visiting. According to the division of Newmark, the tourism text should belong to the text with the vocative function as its main function and the informative function as its secondary function. Therefore, the translation of the tourism text should effectively achieve effects similar to the original text.

From the combing of previous literature, it can be found that Newmark's communicative translation strategy guides many studies on the translation of tourism texts. However, there are few studies on the translation of tourism texts from English to Chinese, and more studies focus on the Chinese-English translation. For this reason, this paper is based on the translation practice of the *Everglades National Park, Florida (Excerpt)* to provide some reference for future English-Chinese translations of tourism.

2.1 Tourism Texts

Tourism text is an important carrier for readers to obtain scenic spot information. Tourism texts stimulate readers' desire to travel by introducing tourist attractions and resources. Its ultimate purpose is to meet readers' expectations and arouse readers' enthusiasm by delivering tourism information. In other words, the dominant function of tourism text is the vocative function. At the same time, tourism texts also provide readers with information they like, from which people can acquire relevant knowledge such as culture and customs, natural geography, etc. Therefore, the informative function is also an important feature. It can be seen that the two most important functions of tourism texts are respectively informative and vocative, whose premise is to provide information and the purpose is to attract tourists.

In addition, we should realize that the translation of tourism texts is a professional translation of tourist attractions and resources for target readers, and its essence is communicative behavior. If the translator fails to deal with the differences between cultures properly, it will often fail to achieve the expected results. Therefore, "more attention should be paid to the accuracy and effectiveness of the information during the translation process, so as to make the translation conform to the target readers' reading habits and aesthetic expectation." This requires the translator to put the reader's acceptance first in the translation process. That is, tourism text translation should realize the conversion from one language to another and consider language barriers and cultural differences. Therefore, to achieve successful communication, translators should flexibly apply various translation strategies and adopt appropriate translation methods according to the text types of tourism texts (Li 2009: 4).

Established in 1974, Everglades National Park covers 2,354 square miles, or 6,097 square kilometers (1.4 million acres). It is located at the tip of southern Florida, the largest subtropical wildlife sanctuary in the continental United States. Everglades National Park protects an unparalleled landscape, providing important habitat for numerous rare and endangered species, such as the manatee, American crocodile, and the elusive Florida panther.

Everglades National Park, Florida (Excerpt) is excerpted from a notice from the U.S. National Park Service about the phased reopening of the park, including alerts of the reopening, activities, safety and accessibility. It can also be regarded as a travel guide, which describes the journey towards people and offers help to the tourists who want to go there. It often includes describing the best travel time, transportation, accommodation, scenic spots and matters needing attention. As a practical text, its main purpose is to introduce and promote tourist scenic spots like the Everglades National Park in Florida. Its evocative and informative functions are very prominent, and it has the characteristics of reader orientation, the effectiveness of information transmission and timeliness.

2.3 Newmark's Translation Theory

Peter Newmark, a well-known translation theorist, is one of the main figures in founding translation studies in the English-speaking world in the 20th century. Newmark devoted himself to studying the past and present of Western translation and put forward his views on

this basis. Newmark's translation theories mainly include the classification of text types, translation approaches, and the late correlative theory of translation.

"According to Karl Bühler's knowledge of language features and Jakobson's classification of them, Newmark proposed six functions of language informative function, expressive function, vocative function, phatic function, aesthetic function, and multilingual function." Then Newmark divided text types into expressive-functional texts, informative-functional texts, and vocative-functional texts (Hou 2020: 49).

After putting forward these three text types, Peter Newmark suggested eight translation approaches or strategies. Firstly, from the perspective of focusing on the source language, he suggested word-for-word translation, literal translation, faithful translation and semantic translation; Secondly, from the perspective of focusing on the target language, he suggested adaptation, free translation, idiomatic translation and communicative translation (Newmark 2001: 45).

In 2007, Newmark came up with a new theory, the correlative theory of translation. It means that "The more serious and important the language of the original or source text, the more closely it should be translated" (Newmark 2007: 113).

In conclusion, Peter Newmark has proposed many significant theories and extensively discussed those concepts, which will greatly influence the translation practice.

Peter Newmark divided text genres into "expressive text", "informative text", and "vocative text". Imaginative literary works, such as poems, songs, novels and dramas, authoritative statements, autobiographies, essays and personal correspondence, etc., are expressive texts. All the formatted texts with science and technology, industry and commerce, and economy as themes belong to informative texts. And vocative text refers to all texts that can infect readers and make them "get information".

Concerning these three kinds of texts, Newmark further creatively proposed the concepts of semantic translation and communicative translation: communicative translation means that the effect of the target text on the reader of the target language is as much as the effect of the original text on the reader of the source language; semantic translation refers to the reproduction of the context of the source text as accurately as possible under the premise of the semantic and syntactic structure of the target language. He believed that only communicative and semantic translation could achieve the two major goals of translation: accuracy and effectiveness.

Newmark made a detailed comparison of the characteristics of semantic translation and communicative translation from different aspects and pointed out that the fundamental difference between them lies in that when the information and the effect conflict, communicative translation lays more emphasis on effect than content. In comparison, semantic translation lays more emphasis on content than effect. Communicative translation can give the translator full freedom. The translator can reorganize the syntax, eliminate the original obscure places in the source language, and make the language conform to the standard of the target language. However, semantic translation emphasizes the content of the information itself, tries to make the form of the target text similar to the form of the original text, and retains the original author's language characteristics and expressive style. Therefore, compared with semantic translation, communicative translation is more

subjective. It can better reflect the translator's creativity, and it attaches great importance to the communicative effect of translation, the key to which is to convey information, make readers of the target language think, act and feel, and play an inductive role in making the translation natural and smooth, and more readable.

Newmark pointed out that the translation of expressive texts should employ semantic translation, while informative and vocative texts communicative translation, which is reader-centred. The most direct purpose of translation of tourism texts is to convey information to readers on the premise of attracting readers' attention and leaving readers with deep memories, so that readers can take action - to visit tourist attractions and pay attention to matters that should be paid attention to. Thus, it can be seen that the tourism text belongs to the vocative text, and the communicative translation should be applied.

To sum up, Newmark's communicative translation focus on the effect that the translation brings to the target language readers, which is of certain guiding significance to the English-Chinese translation of tourism texts.

3. Research Methodology

This research employed a case study focusing on a single unit to produce a detailed and holistic in-depth description (Ary et al., 2018). As indicated, case studies provide an in-depth description of a single unit. The "unit" can be an individual, a group, a site, a class, a policy, a program, a process, an institution, or a community. It is a single occurrence that the researcher is interested in examining. Case studies can answer descriptive questions (what happened) or attempt to explain why something happened by looking at a process. They are particularistic (focused on a particular phenomenon, situation, or event), descriptive (providing a thick, rich description), and heuristic (focused on providing new insights). The researcher believes that something can be learned in this specific case.

In this research, *the Everglades National Park, Florida (Excerpt)* was chosen as the specific unit because it is unique for various reasons. Because the translator wants to achieve a certain communicative purpose, emphasizes the effect and has a specific target audience, the translation has inevitably broken the restrictions of the original text, pursuing smoothness, clarity, directness and conformity with conventions. In this part, the author analyzes the specific application of communicative translation in the translation practice of the excerpt from three aspects: lexical, syntactic and textual analysis.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 At Lexical Level

Generally speaking, there is partial equivalence between English and Chinese; similar expressions in Chinese can replace the meaning of English words or phrases. In the following, two translation methods used in linguistic translation will be introduced: The conversion of part of speech and the translation of public signs.

4.1.1 conversion of part of speech

Example 1:

ST: *There is no shortage of activities for individuals, groups, or families to enjoy outdoors.*

TT: 个人、团体或家庭都能在这找到适合的户外活动。

English belongs to the Indo-European language family, while Chinese is the Sino-Tibetan language family. Many differences exist between English and Chinese in terms of vocabulary and grammatical structure. Therefore, in the process of translating English into Chinese, due to the different ways of expression between English and Chinese some sentences can be translated word by word, while most sentences cannot. In order to make the Chinese translation smooth and natural, some words in the original text need to be converted into different parts of speech in the target text without sticking to the surface structure of the original text. In other words, some words in the original text can be converted into other parts of speech in Chinese on the premise of being faithful to the original meaning and retaining the original effect.

The original sentence uses a nominal phrase "no shortage of" to express the meaning that no matter how many people come together for outdoor activities, there are always options. The translator translates it into a verbal phrase. Everyone can find a suitable outdoor activity here, so that the meaning gets across and the whole sentence flows naturally.

Example 2:

ST: *Accessibility: No immediate trails.*

TT: 如何前往 : 没有路径可直接到达。

English tends to use more nouns with static narratives, while Chinese use more verbs with dynamic ones. The static tendency of English mainly comes from nominalization, a common phenomenon in English. "Nominalization mainly refers to the use of nouns (phrases) to express the information originally expressed by verbs (phrases), such as the use of abstract nouns to express actions, behaviors, changes, states, etc." For example, "accessibility" in Example 2 is an abstract noun, which is used to show the way to one place. Chinese, on the other hand, tend to use verbs. So, in order to better convey the effect and let the reader read without any doubt or discomfort, the translator converted the noun into a verb phrase, that is "如何前往". Likewise, in the noun phrase "no immediate trails", the author wants to say that there is no direct way (to arrive at the destination). When translating, if it is directly translated into a noun phrase "没有直达路", the reader may feel difficult to read. So, if it is translated into "there is no direct path can reach that place", the sentence will be more smoothly and convey the original information and the effect is also retained. (Lian 1993: 105)

4.1.2 Public signs

Examples 3 and 4:

ST: *Things to Do*

TT: 活动介绍

ST: *What you can do*

TT: 解决措施

As mentioned in the theoretical framework above, tourism text belongs to vocative text. As a kind of tourism text, public signs are a special style for specific people to achieve a certain communicative purpose. Its application scope is very wide, almost involved in every aspect of our daily life, such as street signs, billboards, road signs, shop signs, warnings, propaganda,

travel briefs, etc. "As a communicative tool, it conveys necessary and useful information to the public by means of a few words, simple and easy to understand icons or the combination of both." Therefore, it can be seen that public signs feature lots of nouns, verbs, phrases and abbreviations and more often, fixed expression, which means in translation, only concise and idiomatic expression can fully convey the effect of the original text (He 2006: 57).

Just as the example 3, once the original text is translated literally, that is “要做的事情”, it sounds rather awkward, which not only does not convey the meaning of the source text that was intended as an introduction to the activities that can be done, but also may lead the reader to believe that this section is about what is required. However, if it is translated into “活动介绍”, readers can clearly know the main content of this part and can find out the activities they are interested in. This expression is concise and in line with the Chinese language habits. The same is true of example 4.

Example 5 and 6:

ST: *Alligators and crocodiles - Crocodilians are one of the reasons people visit the park, however, these are wild animals that can be dangerous to humans.*

TT: 小心短吻鳄和鳄鱼——鳄鱼是人们参观公园的原因之一，然而，这些野生动物对人类会很危险。

ST: *Poisonous plants - The park's ecosystems support a variety of plant life including some that cause reactions to human skin.*

TT: 警惕有毒植物——公园的生态系统支持多种植物的生长，包括一些会对人类皮肤过敏的植物。

Tourist texts belong to the vocative text, emphasizing the transfer of the effect of the information and the empathy of the reader. This requires the translator to pay attention to the internal logic of the text, modify the translated text to make it clear in the process of tourism translation without sticking to the original form and give full consideration to the core position of readers. Examples 5 and 6 are in the same sentence structure - firstly species are given, and then that the species could be in some danger is pointed out. If it is translated in accordance with the original text word by word, then the front part is just posing out that species. However, if such warning words as “小心” or “警惕” are added, it can let the reader know before he continues reading that this species may be dangerous when visiting, and then with reading below, the reader will know why it is dangerous. This will prepare the reader mentally, and the reading will be smoother.

4.2 At Syntactical Level

Two aspects are included in the syntactic analysis: change of subjects and passive voice, and the punctuation.

4.2.1 Change of subjects and passive voice

Example 7:

ST: *Wading birds, cormorants, Purple Gallinules, and nesting Anhingas may be found along the path anytime of the day during the winter (dry) season.*

TT: 在冬季（旱季），任何时候您都可以在沿路发现涉水鸟类、鸕鹚、紫雀和筑巢的美洲蛇鸟。

English tends to use more impersonal subjects, which means it rarely uses the personal subject to describe but expresses how objective things act on people's perception to things appearing in an objective tone. So, the structure is often like this: "inanimate subject + animate subject". Chinese pays more attention to subjective thinking and often describes objective things from the point of view of oneself, or tends to describe people and their behavior or state, so the personal subject is often used. When the personal subject is clear, Chinese often implies or omits it. Passive voice is a common grammatical phenomenon in English. In some styles, the use of passive sentences has almost become a habit of expression. Passive sentences give rise to the tendency of using impersonal subjects, and vice versa. Chinese uses fewer passive forms. The main reason for this difference is that the use of passive forms in Chinese is limited, and the mark of the passive voice, such as "让", "给", "受", mostly expresses displeasure (Lian 1993: 80).

Therefore, in example 7, the translator transformed the passive voice into the active voice and the impersonal subjects "Wading birds, cormorants, Purple Gallinules, and nesting Anhingas" into the personal subjects "您". What's more, as this tourism text is written for readers, the use of the second person subject can shorten the distance.

Example 8 and 9:

ST: *Wading birds, American Coots, Osprey, White-crowned Pigeons, warblers, Red-shouldered Hawks, Anhingas, rails, Painted Buntings and other transients are best viewed here in the morning.*

TT: 早晨在这里观赏涉禽、美洲骨顶鸡、鱼鹰、白头鸽、莺、赤肩鹭、美洲蛇鸟、秧鸡、彩绘鹇和其他过路的鸟类的效果最好。

ST: *In the summer, fewer programs are offered.*

TT: 夏季提供的项目较少。

Just as said above, English tends to use impersonal subjects and passive voice, while Chinese is exactly the opposite. And when the subject is clear, Chinese often implies or omits it, which is just like example 8 the personal subject "you" is omitted. In example 9, the omitted subject is the national park, and the temporal adverbial phrase "in the summer" becomes the subject in form, which is a common expression in Chinese. That is because subjects in Chinese are not only in various forms, but also dispensable: it can denote giving, receiving, time, place.

4.2.2 Punctuation

Example 10:

ST: *Connecting trails through the Pinelands run 7 miles (11 km) west from the Long Pine Key campground to Pine Glades Lake along the main park road.*

TT: 这些小道从长松岛营地向西延伸7英里（11公里），穿过一片松林地，连通公园主路边松林湖。

English sentences are complicated, and subordination is one of the most important characteristics of modern English, which features right-branching, sentences long and complex, made in "architecture style". Conversely, Chinese sentences are relatively short and commonly use scattered, loose, tight, or composite sentences with parallel structures. Chinese features left-branching, and sentences are made in "chronicle style", using clauses to streamline the thoughts.

So, when there are many prepositional phrases in the original English sentence, the translator can divide the long sentence into several short sentences and recognize those by adding comma, which can help readers sort out the original text's logic and get the main information. The translator divided the original sentence into three sentences using communicative translation. The logical sequence is that "The trails run seven miles (11 kilometers) west from the Long Pine Key campground. Passing through the Pinelands, they lead to Pine Glades Lake along the main park road.", which shows the location of both the Long Pine Key campground, the Pinelands and Pine Glades Lake correctly, leaving no doubt to readers of the target language.

Example 11:

ST: *In keeping with Monroe County's closure order for beaches, North Nest Key and all waters within 100 yards from the shore will be closed for protection of park resources during the holiday weekend. The closure will begin on Friday, July 3 at 6 a.m.*

TT: 根据门罗县对海滩的关闭安排，为保护公园资源，北巢岛和离海岸100码以内的所有水域将自7月3日星期五早上6点起暂停对外开放。

In the original text, two sentences can be combined to make the meaning complete and language pithy in the target language. And it can be taken into consideration to reconstruct them by replacing full stop with comma. By considering communicative translation, the translator put two prepositional phrases in advance as adverbials, which are "in keeping with Monroe County's closure order for beaches" and "for protection of park resources during the holiday weekend", and then turned the second sentence into a temporal adverbial phrase and put it in the main clause as an adverbial. So, the whole structure is "In keeping with Monroe County's closure order for beaches and for protection of park resources during the holiday weekend, North Nest Key and all waters within 100 yards from the shore will be closed from Friday, July 3 at 6 a.m.". By doing so, the information is concisely conveyed, and Chinese readers can well understand it.

4.3 At Textual Level

Discourse refers to the actual language unit used and is the whole language constituted by a series of consecutive paragraphs or sentences in the communication process. "In general, a text consists of words, phrases, sentences and sentence cluster", among which the components were cohesion in form and coherence in semantics (Lan 2020: 19).

Example 12:

ST: *There is no shortage of activities for individuals, groups, or families to enjoy outdoors. The diverse habitats allow for enjoyable activities ranging from hiking, canoeing, kayaking, biking, fresh and saltwater fishing, and camping in the ultimate wilderness.*

TT: 个人、团体或家庭都能在这找到适合的户外活动。无论是步行、乘坐独木舟、划皮划艇、骑自行车，还是在淡水或海水钓鱼、在终极荒野地露营，您都可以饱览多样的自然环境、尽享快乐。

Coherence in a piece of writing refers to the principle that all paragraphs, sentences or ideas are combined so well that they form a united whole. Coherent translation has smooth structural, grammatical, and logical movement from one sentence or idea to the next and the reader does not have to pause and guess at the meaning caused by gaps in development between ideas, sentences and paragraphs.

In example 12, the last topic of the first sentence in the original sentence is outdoor activities, while the subject of the second sentence is the diverse habitats. This is a shift in the topic, which may make the readers pause and guess at the logical relation between them. Therefore, guided by communicative translation, the translator needs to mind the text coherence and make proper adjustments. Out of this, the translator put the activities in the second sentences as the subject of the second sentence in the target text, so that the first sentence can pass through smoothly to the next one, as does readers' understanding.

Example 13:

ST: *Everglades National Park is a popular spot for saltwater and freshwater sport fishing. Boats can be chartered at Flamingo. Be sure to check a visitor center for park fishing regulations and closed areas.*

TT: 大沼泽地国家公园是一个很受欢迎的钓海水鱼和淡水鱼的地方。在弗拉明戈可以租船。在钓鱼之前，一定要阅读游客中心的公园捕鱼规定和封闭区域。

Cohesion is all the grammatical and lexical links that link one part of a text to another. This includes using synonyms, lexical sets, pronouns, verb tenses, time references, grammatical references, etc. For example, 'it', 'neither' and 'this' all refer to an idea previously mentioned.

In example 13, this paragraph mainly talks about fishing in the Everglades National Park, with a topic sentence and two explanatory sentences: one introducing the place for chartering and the other cautions. There are no grammatical or lexical links within these three sentences, and the logic is connected by semantics. Considering well understanding of readers in the target language, the translator added one lexical link, "before fishing" between the last two sentences, to make the reader understand that he or she should read the rules and precautions of fishing before going fishing. Also, with repeating the key word "fishing", the central idea of this whole paragraph is prominent, and the sentences are logically and smoothly linked to express the intended meaning, thus making this paragraph a cohesive group.

5. Conclusion

The tourism text belongs to the vocative text, which focuses on conveying information and effect, so the communicative translation theory should be adopted for this kind of translation. As for this original text, the first part that introduces the outdoor activities belongs to the tourism advertisements, which are descriptive with vivid words. Tourism advertising is infectious, with short words, full of creativity, lively and concise sentence

structure, and strong attraction. At the same time, the announcement informing of the park's operating status is quite a different style. The wording is formal, standard, accurate and stylized. Secondly, the source text involves a wide range of knowledge and a large vocabulary. For example, "hardwood hammock" for "硬木吊床" and "Geocaching" for "寻宝".

Some translation methods can be proposed based on the analysis of examples from lexical, syntactic and textual levels. On the one hand, when translating, some words in the target text can be converted into different parts of speech in the original text to make the language natural and idiomatic. On the other hand, when doing English–Chinese translation,, in most cases, the passive voice should be changed into the active voice, the personal subject is favored in Chinese, and subjects can also be omitted sometimes. Lastly, as English and Chinese have many differences in sentences, the translator should change the order of the sentences sometimes to make them smooth and fluent, and some words can be added to make the meaning coherent.

6. Limitations of the Research

Besides some major findings, there are also many limitations in this translation. Firstly, communicative translation focuses on the effect conveyed by the translation rather than the information, which can easily make the translator ignore some original. So, in the translation, other available translation theories should also be considered to achieve the best translation.

Then, they cannot be translated immediately when translating a text, whether it is a tourism text or a literary work. Relevant information and background should be collected in advance, and otherwise, some mistakes which should be avoided will be made. For example, "Snail Kite (鸂鶒)" might be translated as "蜗牛风筝" if the translator does not look it up in advance.

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